

Pros and Cons of Privatization of Prisons

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Privatization of prison services depends on several factors; the importance of maintaining institutional competence, the core government responsibilities as stipulated in the constitution, if the government agency has the ability to adequately monitor contractors and the positive implications that come with granting government authority to profit-oriented private enterprises. Prison services should be privatized for the many advantages and opportunities they present.

Private prisons offer faster and cheaper bed capacity; they supplement the public facilities in events of overcrowding. Private prisons also give the government time to fast-track its prison building projects (Besser, 2016). Governments use a lot of time in constructing prisons in comparison with private companies since they can negotiate prices of items for bulky purchases. Prison companies can also construct facilities in places that offer economic opportunities to the community, in terms of increasing spending in the community, jobs, and stable employments thereby raising the general economy of the community (Petersen, 2017).

Private prisons also help lower operational costs since they minimize bureaucratic procedures in the completion of simple tasks such as purchasing equipment, recruitment and dismissal of staff (Eason, 2017). Profit-oriented prisons accommodate a larger number of expensive and sensitive female inmates than public ones, cutting the costs of operations for the government.

Private prisons allow for the implementation of new ideas in corrections. They offer the opportunity to test new incarceration philosophies and programs without lengthy approval procedures, as in public prisons (Eason, 2017). The focus, in private prisons, is in treatment rather than control as in public prisons. For instance, if a private prison fails to provide treatment, they are held fully accountable for it. Capitalistic thinking and interests are encouraged by this

treatment and rehabilitation mindset. This mindset creates a sense of legitimacy as it creates a measurable benefit.

However, there is likelihood that those who make profits from incarcerations will lobby and advocate for harsher criminal justice penalties and seek undermine the justice system, a concern voiced by many critics of private prisons. In order to broaden their profit margins, private prison companies actively take part in lobbying geared towards protecting and growing their profits, by working for harsh policies and longer sentences. It is for this reason that private prisons cannot be run like public ones(Eason,2017). The profit motive causes them to deprive inmates. Empirically, private prisons cannot be run like public ones.

Private prisons haven't not only responded to nations' incarceration woes but have also sought to create market conditions, that is more prisoners, necessary to expand their businesses (Petersen, 2017).The total number of people held in private prisons increased recently by over 50% despite a marginal increase in total number of prisons globally. This is a confirmation to Besser's (2016) claims that private prisons rake in tremendous profits annually amounting to billions of dollars..Networking, direct campaign contributions and lobbying are the main three strategies the private prisons industry players use to influence public policy. They spend large sums of money in sponsoring politicians' campaigns and even more on direct lobbying(Eason,2017). They create powerful lobbies that influence legislators to increase the already enormous incarceration level.

Providing public safety is one of the primary responsibilities of a government, therefore, decisions about the ways to achieve public safety should be made on the basis of evidence. Private prison companies have been reported to be spending large sums in efforts that oppose reforms of drug laws, demonstrating that drug war has had a lot of repercussions, and that

imprisoning low-level offenders has been harmful. Countries spend large amounts of money on criminal justice system. These monies are supposed to be used in making citizens safer-not enriching private interests (Besser, 2016). It is morally wrong for corporations to make money off the mass incarcerations of millions of people. In a wider perspective, both private and non-profit prisons vary. There are those with good and bad reputations (Eason, 2017).

References

- Besser, T. L., & Hanson, M. M. (2016). Development of last resort: The impact of new state prisons on small town economies in the United States. *Community Economic Development, 73*.
- Eason, J. M. (2017). Prisons as Panacea or Pariah? The Countervailing Consequences of the Prison Boom on the Political Economy of Rural Towns. *Social Sciences, 6(1), 7*.
- Petersen, O. H., Hjelmar, U., & Vrangbæk, K. (2017). Is Contracting out of Public Services still the Great Panacea? A Systematic Review of Studies on Economic and Quality Effects from 2000 to 2014. *Social Policy & Administration*.